

**GEOLOGY, PROSPECTING AND EXPLORATION OF SOLID MINERALS,
MINERAGENY.**

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Abstract. *The areas of use of lead, zinc and silver are very different. Lead is widely used in the electrical industry, especially for the manufacture of batteries and cable tubes, is used in the aircraft and radio industries, and in mechanical engineering.*

Keywords: *search for polymetallic mineralization.*

**ГЕОЛОГИЯ, ПОИСКИ И РАЗВЕДКА ТВЕРДЫХ ПОЛЕЗНЫХ
ИСКОПАЕМЫХ, МИНЕРАГЕНИЯ.**

Аннотация. *Области применения свинца, цинка и серебра весьма разнообразны. Свинец широко применяется в электротехнической промышленности, особенно для изготовления аккумуляторов и кабельных трубок, применяется в авиационной и радиопромышленности, в машиностроении.*

Ключевые слова: *поиск полиметаллического оруденения.*

Relevance of the research topic. Among other types of minerals, polymetallic (lead-zinc) deposits in Tajikistan are of particular importance. Almost all objects of this mineral in Northern Tajikistan, including Western Karamazar (Takeli and Kansai ore fields) are silver-bearing. This determines the relevance of the research topic. In this regard, a more in-depth study of lead-zinc objects is of great practical and theoretical importance.

The areas of use for lead, zinc and silver are very different. Lead is widely used in the electrical industry, especially for the manufacture of batteries and cable tubes, is used in the aircraft and radio industries, and in mechanical engineering. Because of its ability to absorb X-rays, it is used as protective screens. Paints are also prepared from it, lead oxide is used in metallurgy, glass making and medicine. Zinc is used for the production of galvanized iron, goes to the preparation of brass, bronze, cupronickel and other alloys, in mechanical engineering, the electrical industry, metallurgy, medicine and other sectors of the national economy. Silver is used mainly in the radio-electronic, electrical, food industries, medicine, nanotechnology, as well as in the form of alloys (coins are minted from them, jewelry and household products, laboratory and tableware are made), etc. The widespread use of these metals in the national economy determines the need for prospecting, exploration and production of polymetal deposits.

Research objectives. To achieve this goal, the following tasks were envisaged: a detailed study of the mineral composition of individual ore bodies and deposits of the Takeli and Kansai ore fields as a whole, especially silver mineralization, to identify the typomorphic features of individual minerals or mineral paragenetic associations, and to establish the staging of hydrothermal mineralization.

The degree of scientific development of the problem under study. Studies of the ore content of Karamazar have a long history. The mining industry reached its peak in the Middle Ages (VIII-XII centuries). Numerous mine workings of that time at the Kansai, Jerkamar, Takeli and other deposits testify to this. However, information on the conduct of scientific research at that time is very scarce. After a long break (until the end of the 19th century), we find the first

information about the ore content of Kansai in the works of G.D. Romanovsky. At the beginning of the 20th century, V.N. Tomilin and A.A. Andreev, summarizing the available information, compile a catalog of the minerals of Turkestan. The systematic study of the Western Karamazar begins in 1925-1927. At this time, they begin a detailed geological study and exploration work, and already in 1931, the Kansai, Dagani Darbaza and Takeli deposits begin to be developed. In the future, many researchers began to study the deposits of the Western Karamazar, such as I.V. Dyugaev, B.N. Nasledov, A.V. Korolev, F.Ch. Ziyaev, F.I. Wolfson, Z.A. Koroleva, E.D. Karpova, Kh.M. Abdullaev, Z.M. Protodyakonova, I.V. Dubrova, A.A. Filimonova, V.A. Zharikov, Z.M. Protodyakonov and V.S. Popov. The works of these researchers provide information about the geology, stratigraphy, tectonics, magmatism, petrography, mineralogy, ore content, and metallogeny of the polymetallic deposits of Western Karamazar. In the Takeli and Kansai ore fields, despite the rather detailed geological study, little attention was paid to the mineral composition of the ores, especially the silver content.

GENERAL CHARACTERISTICS OF THE STUDY

Purpose of the study. The main goal of the dissertation work is a detailed study of the mineral composition of ores using the latest methods of analysis and the conditions for their formation in order to develop prospecting and evaluation criteria in the search for polymetallic mineralization.

Research objectives. To achieve this goal, the following tasks were envisaged: a detailed study of the mineral composition of individual ore bodies and deposits of the Takeli and Kansai ore fields as a whole, especially silver mineralization, to identify the typomorphic features of individual minerals or mineral paragenetic associations, establish the staging of hydrothermal mineralization, and determine thermobarogeochemical parameters mineral formation, determination of genetic and age characteristics of lead-zinc mineralization.

Research objects. are the polymetallic deposits of the Takeli and Kansai ore fields.

The subject of the study. are the mineral composition of ores and thermobarogeochemical conditions for the formation of polymetallic deposits.

Scientific novelty of the research. For the first time, the latest analytical methods were used for the deposits of the Kansai and Takeli ore fields, which made it possible to refine and supplement the composition of the mineral complex. A detailed study of the mineral composition made it possible to discover two silver minerals that were not previously described in these deposits (pierseite and polybasite). Paragenetic associations of minerals have been identified and the stages of mineralization formation have been somewhat clarified, the temperature intervals for crystallization of polymetallic and silver mineralization have been determined, with the establishment of a vertical paleotemperature gradient.

Theoretical significance of the study. The data on silver finds within the Kansai and Takeli ore fields, which were previously presented in the literature in a scattered form, are summarized. The typomorphic features of minerals and the temperature range of the formation of the main ore and silver mineralization in combination with a vertical paleotemperature gradient are revealed. It has been established that the most optimal temperature for the formation of silver mineralization is 260°-125°C.

Scientific and practical significance of the study. The results obtained can be used in solving applied problems of geology. The identified complex of thermobarogeochemical features

of mineral formation at the deposits of the Kansai and Takeli ore fields is applicable not only in the search and evaluation of new objects within the studied ore fields, but also for similar objects in other areas, which will allow more efficient prospecting and evaluation work on relatively poorly studied objects.

Provisions for defense:

1. A detailed mineralogical study of the deposits of the Kansai and Takeli ore fields makes it possible to clarify the mineral composition of ore and vein formations.

2. Identification of the typomorphic features of individual minerals and paragenetic associations makes it possible to establish the wide distribution of silver mineralization.

3. An analysis of the stages of hydrothermal mineralization allows us to speak of four stages of mineral formation: I - sulfide, II - carbonate, III - sulfide-quartz, IV - carbonate-fluorite-barite. Determining the thermobarogeochemical parameters of mineral formation makes it possible to establish the temperature of mineral formation, the presence of a vertical temperature gradient, and also to clarify the genetic features of lead-zinc mineralization.

4. The material composition, thermobarogeochemical parameters of mineral formation, structural and textural features, wall-rock alterations of host rocks indicate that skarns played the role of host environment, but did not directly participate in ore formation.

The degree of reliability of the results. It is confirmed by the use of a complex of methods of mineralogical-thermobarogeochemical studies, as well as by the representativeness of the factual material. More than 500 samples, 85 polished sections were studied. More than 200 double-sided polished plates of minerals and mineral punches were made and studied. More than 300 determinations of the temperatures of homogenization of inclusions of mineral-forming fluids in minerals, 15 analyzes of water extracts, more than 60 chemical, 28 atomic absorption analyzes were carried out. Also, the degree of reliability is confirmed by approbation of the results obtained at scientific events of various levels and their publication, using both published literature data and stock materials of the Main Geological Department under the Government of the Republic of Tajikistan.

Compliance of the dissertation with the passport of the scientific specialty. The content of the research of this dissertation corresponds to points 1, 3 and 4 in the specialty 25.00.11 - "Geology, prospecting and exploration of solid minerals, minerageny":

- conditions for the formation of deposits of solid minerals;
- metallogeny and minerageny: general, regional and special, purpose and tasks;
- forecast, prospecting, exploration and geological and economic evaluation of deposits.

CONCLUSION

1. Sulfide ores of the Takeli and Kansai ore fields contain a very peculiar complex of minerals. They contain a large number of both hypogene and supergene minerals. In the Takeli ore field, 37 minerals are described, of which 19 are hypogene and 18 are supergene. In the Kansai ore field, 48 minerals are described, among which 19 are hypogene and 29 are supergene. The main minerals of both ore fields are galena and sphalerite. Pyrite, chalcopyrite and fahlore are of secondary importance. In deposits of the Takeli ore field, in addition, arsenopyrite is developed. Of the supergene minerals, the most developed are goethite, hydrogoethite, cerussite, anglesite, and smithsonite.

2. On the Takeliysky ore field, from the actual silver minerals, 5 were found - native silver, argentite, proustite, pyrargyrite, polybasite. In addition, Ag-tetrahedrite is described, in which the amount of silver varies from 2.20 to 3.45, averaging 2.92 wt %.

3. Studies show that in the Kansai ore field, silver carriers are mainly silver minerals proper, such as native silver, argentite, hessite, pyrargyrite, proustite, stromeyerite, stephanite, pierseite, polybasite, miargyrite, argentopyrite and kerargyrite [3-A].

4. It has been established that in ore minerals - galena, chalcopyrite and fahlore, silver is isomorphically included in their structure. For example, in Takeley galena, the silver concentration ranges from 676 to 3800 g/t, averaging 1424.6 g/t, in chalcopyrites, the average silver content is 667 g/t, and in tetrahedrites, the average silver content is 2.92 wt.%.

5. Polymetallic mineralization in the deposits of Western Karamazar occurred as a result of a staged process of mineral formation with repeated opening of fault systems.

6. It has been established that ore formation occurred as a result of 4 stages: sulfide, carbonate, sulfide-quartz and carbonate-fluorite-barite. The bulk of polymetallic mineralization is associated with sulfide stages.

7. Thermobarogeochemical studies have established that the process of post-magmatic mineral formation occurred in the temperature range of 450-90°C with a paleotemperature gradient of 8-14°C per 100 m of depth. The results of the analysis of aqueous extracts revealed that the solutions were initially bicarbonate-calcium, sulfate-calcium-sodium and sulfate-chloride-calcium-sodium-magnesium and, in the final stage, bicarbonate-calcium.

8. Silver mineralization was formed at temperatures from 260 to 125°C, mainly from sulfate, bicarbonate, bicarbonate-calcium solutions with an insignificant content of chlorine, sulfate ion, sodium and potassium.

9. The material composition, thermobarogeochemical parameters of mineral formation, structural and textural features, near-ore changes in host rocks, and other features of ore formation indicate hydrothermal conditions for the formation of polymetallic ores in both the Takeli and Kansai ore fields.

REFERENCES

1. Balashov Yu.A. Geoximiya redkozemelnykh elementov. -M.: Nauka, 1976.-267 s.
2. Borodin L.S. Petroximiya magmaticheskix seriy. –M.: Nauka, 1987. – 262 s.
3. Verbiskiy P.G. Osnovy kristallooptiki i metody izucheniya mineralov pod mikroskopom. – Kiyev: Izd. Kiyevskogo universiteta, 1967
4. Geologiyadan ruscha-o‘zbekcha lug‘at //T.N.Dolimov va b. –Toshkent: O‘zbekiston, 1995.-240 b.
5. Geodinamika Tyan-Shanya /Dalimov T.N., Ganiyev I.N., Shpotova L.V., Kadyrov M.X.. – Tashkent: Universitet, 1993. – 207 s.
6. Dalimov T.N., Ayzenshtat V.I. Fasialnost granitoidnykh formasiy Uzbekistana.- Tashkent: Fan, 1972.- 226 s.
7. Dalimov T.N. Kislyu vulkanizm skladchatykh oblastey (na primere Sredinnogo i Yujnogo Tyan-Shanya). – Tashkent: Fan, 1981. – 296 s.
8. Dolimov T.N., Troiskiy V.I. Evolyusion geologiya. “O‘qituvchi” NMIU, Toshkent, 2007. 368 b.